

PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR USING INNOVATIVE APPROACHES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract:

This article discusses pedagogical technologies based on innovative approaches necessary for teaching a foreign language. The use of modern technologies, interactive methods, and new methodological literature and instructions in teaching a foreign language in educational institution is of great importance. It will be introduced to how the effective use of these new innovative approaches can help expand the teacher's knowledge and ability to teach and engage students in foreign languages.

Key words: Innovation, education, foreign language, English, innovative technologies, learning, Internet, methods, teaching.

Nowadays, the main attention is focused on the students, their personality and their unique inner world. Therefore, the selection of the main methods and tasks of a modern teacher, the optimal level of the students' learning activity is being set for the purpose of personal development. In today's rapidly developing era, science and technology are also growing rapidly. Progress is taking place in every field. In particular, great changes and significant achievements are being science. Delevering each subject to students using new innovative pedagogical technologies is one of the main requirements of today's education. The need to learn foreign languages is increasing not only around the world but also in Uzbekistan. It is the duty of teachers to provide effective pedagogical skills.

Especially after the adoption of the Resolution of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Abduganievich Karimov No.1875 dated December 13, 2012 the attention paid to the teaching and learning of foreign languages has increased. A new stage, a new era in study of foreign languages has begun in our country. The main goal of teaching foreign languages is to preserve and develop the communicative culture of schoolchildren, to teach them to practically master a foreign language[3].

In general, pedagogy is rapidly developing concepts such as innovative activity, innovative pedagogy, management of innovative processes in education, learning foreign languages, teaching in a foreign language have appeared. The teaching of foreign languages, especially English, in educational institutions is connected with the creation of innovative educational theory. This is the reason for forming an attitude to the child in the process of education, in order to achieve certain successes in the educational efficiency, to ensure the socialization of the individual, to reform the educational system by introducing pedagogical technologies into the educational system[2].

Currently, the demand for English as a foreign language is increasing in every field. High-quality educational programs are provided by qualified teachers to improve English language skills from basic grammar to advanced levels. Skills for effective use and implementation are being developed. Various internet resources are of great help in developing reading, writing, listening, and speaking skills in English, and of course, there are many students who achieved excellent results using electronic learning programs and textbooks during classes.

In learning a foreign language, a step-by-step approach based on the student's level productivity and gives good results. For each stage, a special active program is developed by the teacher. Active methods of teaching help to motivate students to think actively and engage in practical activities during the learning process of physical education, and help them master the material. For each stage of the lesson, it is necessary to consider active methods that are effective for not only teachers, but also for students[1].

Here are some of the most effective innovative pedagogical technologies are:
 communicative approach- teaching the language as a means of communication;
 interactive methods- discussion, role-playing, and group activities;
 gamification (game-based learning)- increasing student engagement and motivation;
 mobile applications and online platforms- Duolingo, Memorise, Quizlet, Moodle Google Classroom, etc;

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artificial intelligence and virtual reality- chatbots, VR/AR technologies in language learning.

As we noted above, using these technological approaches in the teaching process helps to achieve high results. If a teacher organizes and plans each day's lesson based on such methods, students' interest in the language will increase.

The role of modern technology is remarkable in language learning and teaching. The use of technological means helps to learn every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, listening, writing and speaking). For example, it is impossible to perform this process without a computer, player or CD. To improve listening, you should watch various videos and movies. To improve speaking skills, it is very useful to organize online chats and debates, in addition, to improve writing skills, it is more effective to read various articles and ready-made essay samples from the Internet and analyze them as a group. Also, for reading skills, it is one of the best approaches to analyze each question and read more books.

The use of the innovative approaches in education helps improve students' efficiency, enhance their comprehension levels, and make learning more engaging and interactive. In particular, modern technologies and new pedagogical methods play a crucial role in teaching foreign language.

Innovative approaches and their effectiveness:

1. Blended learning- combines traditional classroom lessons with online education. The advantages of this method include:

students can study the materials independently at convenient time;

teachers can focus more on practical exercises rather than repeating theoretical concepts;

online platforms provide access to additional materials, tests, and video lessons[5].

2. Flipped classroom- in this method, students study the main learning materials independently before class, while the lesson itself is dedicated to practical exercises, discussion, and interactive tasks:

students actively participate in discussions and problem-solving activities, improving their critical thinking skills;

it allows for more personalized teacher support since class time is used for interactive engagement rather than passive lectures[6].

3. Adaptive learning- leverages artificial intelligence to personalize the learning experience based on each student's progress and notes;

it helps students focus on their weak areas by adjusting content difficulty dynamically;

AI-driven platforms provide instant feedback, enhancing the learning process;

this approach is especially useful in language learning, where students can receive customized grammar and vocabulary exercises[4].

As a result of numerous studies, the demand for the above innovative approaches is increasing day by day.

In conclusion, nowadays, teaching foreign languages, especially English, using innovative methods of teaching in educational system and educational institutions is gaining importance. In a word, innovation means a new approach to solving a problem in a specific field of activity. Teaching each grammatical topic or different sentence structures based on new pedagogical technologies, while moving away from old approaches, will also create ease for the future generation. In general, innovative approaches in teaching foreign languages serve to make the educational process more effective, interactive and productive. In the future, it will be important for the education system to support these technologies more widely.

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